

Unraveling the origins and P-T-t evolution of the allochthonous Sobrado unit (Órdenes Complex, NW Spain) using combined U–Pb titanite, monazite and zircon geochronology and rare-earth element (REE) geochemistry

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Abstract. The Sobrado unit, within the upper part of the Órdenes Complex (NW Spain) represents an allochthonous tectonic slice of exhumed high-grade metamorphic rocks formed during a complex sequence of orogenic processes in the middle to lower crust. In order to constrain those processes, U–Pb geochronology and rare-earth element (REE) analyses of accessory minerals in migmatitic paragneiss (monazite, zircon) and mylonitic amphibolites (titanite) were conducted using laser ablation split stream inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LASS-ICP-MS). The youngest metamorphic zircon age obtained coincides with a Middle Devonian concordia monazite age (~ 380 Ma) and is interpreted to represent the minimum age of the Sobrado high-P granulite facies metamorphism that occurred during the early stages of the Variscan orogeny. Metamorphic titanite from the mylonitic amphibolites yield a Late Devonian age (~ 365 Ma) and track the progressive exhumation of the Sobrado unit. In zircon, cathodoluminescence images and REE analyses allow two aliquots with different origins in the paragneiss to be distinguished. An Early Ordovician age (~ 490 Ma) was obtained for metamorphic zircons, although with a large dispersion, related to the evolution of the rock. This age is considered to mark the onset of granulite fa-

cies metamorphism in the Sobrado unit under intermediate-P conditions, and related to intrusive magmatism and coeval burial in a magmatic arc setting. A maximum depositional age for the Sobrado unit is established in the late Cambrian (~ 511 Ma). The zircon dataset also record several inherited populations. The youngest cogenetic set of zircons yields crystallization ages of 546 and 526 Ma which are thought to be related to the peri-Gondwanan magmatic arc. The additional presence of inherited zircons older than 1000 Ma is interpreted as suggesting a West African Craton provenance.

1 Introduction

Zircon, monazite and titanite are accessory mineral phases found in rocks with a very wide range of compositions. These minerals can resist numerous sedimentary, igneous and metamorphic events across a wide range of temperatures, pressures and strains, even when fluids are present. Frequently, compositional domains can be defined in these minerals that record changes in different parameters (Storey et al., 2007; Castiñeiras et al., 2010; Stübner et al., 2014;

Hacker et al., 2015; Stearns et al., 2016; Stipska et al., 2016). These minerals additionally provide several closed decay chains or disintegration systems ($^{238}\text{U} \rightarrow ^{206}\text{Pb}$, $^{235}\text{U} \rightarrow ^{207}\text{Pb}$ y $^{232}\text{Th} \rightarrow ^{208}\text{Pb}$), because they hold variable concentrations of uranium (U) and/or thorium (Th) in their crystal lattices. Such variations in concentration allow accurate dating using microscopic-scale analysis (tens of micrometers).

Titanite is stable in metabasites across a wide range of metamorphic conditions (Spear, 1981; Frost et al., 2000) and is able to record metamorphic and deformational events (Franz and Spear, 1985; Verts and Frost, 1996; Rubatto and Hermann, 2001; Spencer et al., 2013; Stearns et al., 2015, 2016). The titanite U/Pb system is a widely used geochronometer for deformation events in granulite–amphibolite facies rocks (Spear, 1981; Cherniak, 2006; Harlov et al., 2006). Monazite is common in amphibolite and higher-grade facies. Zoning in this mineral can have an igneous or metamorphic origin (DeWolf et al., 1993; Hawkins and Bowering, 1997; Zhu et al., 1997; Spear and Pyle, 2002). The crystallization stages seen in zoned monazite, with changes in Y, Ca, Si, Sr, Ba, rare-earth elements (REEs), U and Th, has been linked to certain metamorphic reactions (Kohn and Malloy, 2004; Corrie and Kohn, 2008) or deformation process (Terry and Hamilton, 2000). Zircon survives the majority of magmatic, metamorphic and erosive terrestrial processes. Cathodoluminescence analysis of zircon zoning patterns allows a large variety of reactions to be distinguished and can clarify the petrogenetic evolution (Corfu et al., 2003). Th/U ratios can also be used to separate zircon based on their igneous or metamorphic origin (Hoskin and Ireland, 2000; Möller et al., 2002; Hokada and Harley, 2004; Hoskin, 2005). REE abundances can also be used as a qualitative petrological indicator (Belousova et al., 2002). Heavy rare-earth elements (HREEs) are preferentially incorporated into zircon compared to light rare-earth elements (LREEs). Hence, the normalized HREE slope can be used to interpret whether a zircon crystallized or recrystallized when garnet and xenotime (YPO_4) were present, because these minerals also preferentially assimilate HREE in the lattice (Hoskin and Ireland, 2000; Rubatto, 2002; Hermann and Rubatto, 2003; Rubatto et al., 2009).

The events recorded in individual grains can be radiometrically dated employing combined laser ablation analyses and cathodoluminescence (CL) images in zircons (Corfu et al., 2003) and compositional maps obtained using electron microprobe (EMPA) in monazite (Gonçalves et al., 2005; Williams et al., 2007) to recognize different growth zones. The chemical analysis, especially REE, links the development of growth zones to specific metamorphic or deformational events (Frost et al., 2000; Rubatto, 2002; Whitehouse and Platt, 2003; Zheng et al., 2007; Chen et al., 2010; Gagnevin and Daly, 2010; Holder et al., 2015). Simultaneous geochronology and REE data are a powerful tool in the inter-

pretation of ages – this is known as REE-assisted geochronology (Castiñeiras et al., 2010).

This methodology has been applied to selected samples of the Sobrado unit (Fig. 1), which forms part of the allochthonous complexes of NW Spain and one where the structural and metamorphic evolution is rather well known (de Pablo Maciá et al., 1984; Díaz García et al., 1999; Arenas and Martínez Catalán, 2002; Benítez-Pérez, 2017). This unit occurs in the upper allochthon of the Órdenes Complex and represents a tectonic slice of exhumed ultramafics, eclogites, high-P granulites, amphibolites and migmatitic paragneiss derived from a peri-Gondwanan terrane. It evolved along a complex sequence of geological processes involving Cambrian–Ordovician rifting with voluminous bimodal plutonism, nearly contemporaneous granulite facies metamorphism of intermediate-P, early Variscan subduction and subsequent exhumation by ductile thrusting during Variscan collision with the external margin of northern Gondwana.

Previous geochronological data on the Sobrado unit include U–Pb ages from four samples (Fernández-Suárez et al., 2002, 2007). A middle Cambrian protolith age of a gabbro and a Middle Devonian metamorphic age of a high-P basic granulite supposedly derived from the same gabbro were obtained by zircon dating. Zircon in a migmatitic, mylonitized paragneiss yielded discordant ages with an Early Ordovician lower intercept, while monazite dating provided Cambrian–Ordovician ages in another migmatitic, mylonitized paragneiss. This new study aims at constraining the metamorphic evolution of the unit including dating a migmatitic paragneiss, as previous data missed the early Variscan ages found in intercalated high-P granulites, and also an amphibolite, which could date advanced stages of exhumation. Monazite and zircon ages of paragneiss and titanite ages of amphibolites taken from separate but presently adjacent tectonic slices of the high-P/high-T (HP-HT) of the Sobrado unit are compared and interpreted using REE-assisted geochronology. This sheds new light upon the possible origin, ages and relationships between the regional foliation development and the partial melting processes that have occurred in this and equivalent units of the NW Iberian upper allochthon.

2 Geological background

The allochthonous complexes in NW Spain are remnants of a huge nappe stack preserved as klippen in the core of late Variscan synforms. They consist of units mostly of peri-Gondwanan derivation, which can be classified in three groups based on their structural position in the tectonic pile and origin: the upper, middle and lower allochthons (Fig. 1).

The upper allochthon is a piece of the northern margin of Gondwana detached and drifted away during the Cambrian–Ordovician opening of the Rheic Ocean. The middle allochthon is formed by lithospheric pieces of oceanic affinity or oceanic supracrustal sequences that formed part of the

Figure 1. (a) Simplified map of the Variscan orogen in Europe with the location of the Órdenes Complex. (b) Map of the Órdenes Complex with indication of the main units and tectonic contacts. Extensional detachments are labeled: BPSD: Bembibre–Pico Sacro system; CD: Corredoiras; FD: Fornás; PCD: Ponte Carreira. Figure 2 location is indicated.

Rheic oceanic realm and are often referred to as ophiolitic units. The lower allochthon derives from distal parts of the Gondwanan continental margin.

The allochthon units are separated from the Iberian autochthon by a series of kilometer-scale imbricated sheets, known as the parautochthon (Ribeiro et al., 1990), or Schistose Domain in Galicia (NW Spain), consisting of a set of Paleozoic metasedimentary and volcanic rocks. The parautochthon has stratigraphic and igneous affinities with the Iberian autochthon of the Central Iberian Zone, and no ophiolites occur between them. For these reasons, it is interpreted as a distal part of the Gondwanan continental margin (Farias et al., 1987; Dias da Silva et al., 2014).

The allochthonous units are regarded as a stack of Variscan thrust sheets with associated tectonic fabrics and metamorphic events. Due to the “piggy-back” nature of the sequence, the structurally higher units are thought to represent

the furthest traveled paleogeographic domains. Recumbent folds, thrusts and extensional detachments formed during the Variscan collision are found in all three allochthonous units (Martínez Catalán et al., 1999; Gómez-Barreiro et al., 2007).

Maximum sedimentation ages obtained from the study of detrital zircon carried out in metasediments from the upper allochthon can be estimated between 530 and 510 Ma (e.g., Fuenlabrada et al., 2010). Intrusive rocks in the upper allochthon have been dated between 520 and 490 Ma and are associated with the development of a magmatic arc which evolves into an extensional scenario that ended with the opening of the Rheic Ocean (Peucat et al., 1990; Ordóñez Casado, 1998; Abati et al., 1999, 2007; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007; Castiñeiras et al., 2010). Two high-*P*/high-*T* metamorphic events have been recognized in this unit. The oldest one has yielded ages of 490–480 Ma (Kuijper 1979; Peucat et al. 1990; Abati et al., 1999, 2007; Fernández-Suárez

et al., 2002) and the youngest one has been dated approximately between 405 and 390 Ma (Santos Zalduegui et al., 1996; Ordóñez Casado et al., 2001; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007). In the middle allochthon, crystallization ages vary between 390 and 375 Ma (Peucat et al., 1990; Dallmeyer et al., 1991, 1997), and ages from 375 to 365 Ma have been related to continental subduction (Santos Zalduegui et al., 1995; Abati et al., 2010). Thrust wedge collapse, in the middle and lower allochthonous units, is thought to have happened between 390 and 365 Ma, followed by a collision in the internal zones around 365–330 Ma, causing further folding and thrusts (Dallmeyer et al., 1997; Martínez Catalán et al., 2009). Afterwards, there was another extensional collapse phase until 315 Ma, followed by a final phase of shortening and folding up until approximately 305 Ma related to the regional oroclinal bending in Spain (Aerden, 2004; Martínez Catalán, 2011, 2012; Álvarez-Valero et al., 2014).

The upper allochthon is further subdivided into high-P/high-T and intermediate-P units (Gómez Barreiro et al., 2007). The present study focuses on two of the high-P/high-T upper units (Figs. 1 and 2). The origin of the high-P event recorded in these units is controversial but might reflect the accretion of the units into the continental part of northern Gondwana, during the Early–Middle Devonian (400–390 Ma; Ballèvre et al., 2014).

The Sobrado antiform consists of three tectonic slices bounded by two extensional detachments (Figs. 1 and 2). The lower tectonic slice comprises highly serpentinized ultramafic rocks with interlayered metabasite units. The metabasites include eclogites ($\text{Omp} + \text{Grt} + \text{Qtz} + \text{Rt} \pm \text{Ky}$ and Zo , mineral abbreviations according to Whitney and Evans, 2010) and related clinopyroxene-garnet rocks without primary plagioclase ($\text{Cpx} + \text{Grt} + \text{Qtz} + \text{Rt} \pm \text{Zo}$), as well as other types of rocks derived from the retrogression and mylonitization of the early high-P stages. The intermediate tectonic slice is made up of migmatitic felsic gneiss (mainly paragneiss), with frequent inclusions of high-P granulites ($\text{Cpx} + \text{Grt} + \text{Pl} + \text{Qtz} + \text{Rt} \pm \text{Ky}$). Remnants of igneous protoliths are not preserved either in the lower or intermediate tectonic slices. The upper tectonic slice, however, contains migmatitic felsic gneiss and mafic layers derived from deformed and recrystallized gabbros with locally preserved relict igneous textures, reaching high-P granulite facies conditions. The progressive transformation from gabbros to high-P granulites ($\text{Na-Di} + \text{Grt} + \text{Pl} + \text{Qtz} + \text{Rt}$) has occurred in a series of different stages with a metamorphic peak at 13–17 kbar and 660–770 °C (Arenas and Martínez Catalán, 2002).

The metamorphic evolution of the Sobrado unit as described in the literature indicates that felsic gneiss underwent differing degrees of partial melting after the metabasites reached their peak pressure. Consequently, the felsic gneiss is thought to have developed a regional foliation under amphibolite facies conditions, as did the amphibolite gneiss, “flaser” amphibolites and fine-grained amphi-

bolites. This metamorphic evolution is described by Arenas and Martínez Catalán (2002) as a clockwise P–T path, with a metamorphic peak of, at least, 15 kbar and > 800 °C, followed by an isothermal decompression. This trajectory is interpreted to result from gravitational collapse of an over-thickened orogenic wedge (Gómez-Barreiro et al., 2007; Ballèvre et al., 2014). Although some regional structures, such as the Fornás detachment (FD, Fig. 1; Gómez-Barreiro et al., 2007; Álvarez-Valero et al., 2014) or the Corredoiras detachment (CD, Fig. 1; Díaz García et al., 1999), have been related to this gravitational readjustment, no study has dealt with the development of the extensional fabrics in any detail. Overall, it is thought that the extensional flow has generated a pervasive thinning of the orogenic pile and that the preserved sequence of tectonic slices is strongly condensed.

3 Sample description and methodology

3.1 Selected samples

Two representative samples (JBP-71-15A and JBP-71-21) were selected from two structurally separate but currently adjacent parts of the high-P/high-T Sobrado unit, within the Órdenes Complex, for laser ablation (laser ablation split stream; LASS) analyses, including U–Pb geochronology and REE determinations. The samples locations are presented in Fig. 2.

Sample JBP-71-21 is a mylonitic fine-grained amphibolite, without any preserved igneous relicts. Fine-grained amphibolites represent an advanced stage in the mylonitization of the metabasites. They appear as relatively thin layers inside the mafic rocks and dominate in a thick mylonitic layer (300–700 m; Fig. 2; Arenas and Martínez Catalán, 2002; Benítez Pérez, 2017) located at the base of the upper tectonic slice. The sample comprises $\text{Hbl} + \text{Pl} + \text{Grt} \pm \text{Cpx} + \text{Bt} \pm \text{Rt} \pm \text{Ttn} \pm \text{Ilm} \pm \text{Zo} \pm \text{Qtz}$ (Fig. 3). Mylonitic foliation and lineation are defined by amphibole and plagioclase (Fig. 3). Garnet appears as subrounded porphyroclasts partially resorbed (Fig. 3). Titanite grains are parallel to the foliation and in textural equilibrium with plagioclase and amphibole. Rutile and ilmenite are always hosted as inclusions both in titanite and/or garnet (Fig. 3c, d).

Sample JBP-71-15A is a granulite facies migmatitic paragneiss from the underlying intermediate tectonic slice. It comprises $\text{Qtz} + \text{Pl} + \text{Grt} + \text{Kfs} + \text{Ky} + \text{Bt} + \text{Ilm} + \text{Rt}$ and shows microscopic-scale textural evidence of partial melting. Temperature and pressure estimation ranges are 750–850 °C and 11–16 kbar for the anatectic fabric (Benítez-Pérez, 2017). Leucocratic domains with Qtz, Kfs and Pl, with evidence of plastic deformation define the foliation and Bt, Ky, Rt and Grt define linear aggregates resulting in a pervasive lineation (Fig. 4). Along the strained leucosomes, garnets show evidence of plastic deformation (Benítez Pérez, 2017) like (Fig. 4a, f, g): sigmoidal, dumbbell-shaped grains

Figure 2. Geological map of the study area and location of the samples, modified from Arenas and Martínez Catalán (2002): (a) location of the Ordenes Complex within the Iberian massif. (b) Sobrado unit map, indicating units and tectonic slices. (c) Cross-section in the WNW–ESE direction and (d) SW–NE and SSW–NNE directions of the Sobrado antiform. Sample locations are indicated.

Figure 3. Fine-grained amphibolites (sample JBP-71-21) from the basal mylonitic band in the Sobrado upper tectonic slice. (a) Hornblende–plagioclase mixtures and titanite with preferred orientation, defining the mylonitic fabric. (b) Main fabric surrounding a garnet porphyroblast. Note that titanite is the Ti phase in the mylonitic fabric but ilmenite grains have been preserved inside the garnet. The position of panel (c) is indicated by a dashed white square. (c) Garnet inclusions from panel (b) where ilmenite inclusions show a progressive breakdown into titanite ($Ilm < Ttn$). Note ilmenite inclusions inside pristine garnet areas show no evidence of transformation. (d) Inclusions of rutile inside titanite and partial transformation of plagioclase into zoisite. All micrographs are in plane-polarized light (PPL). (Mineral abbreviations are after Whitney and Evans, 2010; Hbl: hornblende, Ttn: titanite, Ilm: ilmenite, Rt: rutile, Pl: plagioclase, Zo: zoisite, Grt: garnet.)

Figure 4. Granulite facies migmatitic paragneiss from the Sobrado middle tectonic slice (Fig. 2). (a) General microstructure where leucosome bands and preferred orientation of elongated garnets, biotite, rutile and kyanite define the foliation. (b) Zircon elongated grain in recrystallized leucosome domain. Main inclusions in garnet include rutile, ilmenite and zircon (PPL) and (c) cross-polarized light (CPL). (d) Monazite and zircon subrounded grain in the leucosome domain. (e) Subrounded elongated grain of zircon included in a garnet. (f) Plastically deformed garnet (sigmoidal grain) in a leucosome. Zircon and monazite are found in the quartz-rich area around the garnet. (g) Sigmoidal garnet in a leucosome. Inclusions of prismatic and bipyramidal zircons and rutile are observed. (h) Monazite grain in a garnet pressure shadow with biotite. Ky: kyanite, Bt: biotite, Qtz: quartz, Kfs: K-feldspar, Pl: plagioclase, Rt: rutile, Zrn: zircon, Mnz: monazite, Grt: garnet.

and pinch-and-swell microstructures (Ji and Martignole, 1994; Kleinschrot and Duyster, 2002; Passchier and Trouw, 2005). Zircon and monazite are found in different microtextural settings. Small elongated prisms of zircon are always found shielded within garnets (Fig. 4g), while relatively larger zircon grains with irregular, elongated, subrounded shapes, appear across the fabric in leucosomes, biotite aggregates and even within kyanite crystals (Fig. 4a, b, c, d, f). In a few cases, elongated/subrounded zircons have been found as inclusions in garnets (Fig. 4e). Monazite grains show elongated to subrounded grains located in Qtz–Kfs–Pl–Bt domains, which define the main foliation of the rock (Fig. 4d, f, h).

3.2 Sample preparation

Sample preparation was carried out at the laboratories of the Universidad Complutense (Madrid). The rocks were crushed, pulverized and sieved to achieve a 0.1–0.5 mm grain size. Heavy minerals were concentrated using a Wilfley™ table. The non-magnetic minerals from this heavy fraction are then separated using a Frantz isodynamic magnetic separator. A final concentrated fraction is obtained using heavy liquids (methylene iodide, CH₂I₂).

Zircon (translucent, colorless or light brown), monazite (yellow) and titanite (colorless) grains are selected by hand-picking, according to their external morphology viewed under a binocular microscope. All the grains collected were arranged separately in parallel rows, mounted on glass slide with a double-sided adhesive and set in epoxy resin. After the

resin was cured, the surface was eroded using a wet abrasive silicon carbide abrasive paper (4000 grit) and polished with 0.3 μm aluminum oxide. The surface was then coated with gold, to avoid charging problems under the scanning electron microscope (SEM). Prior to isotopic analysis, CL images of zircon grains were taken on a JEOL JSM-820 SEM, and compositional maps of monazite grains were created on a JEOL Superprobe JXA-8900M microprobe (National Center for Electron Microscopy, Madrid). Secondary electron (SE) images were also taken to determine the exact location of the spots and identify the internal structure and presence of inclusions and defects in zircon, monazite and titanite grains.

3.3 Mineral description

Titanite grains are generally rounded, with an average grain size of 100 μm and irregular morphologies. Their secondary electron images reveal homogeneous compositions and the presence of solid inclusions. This grain size permits large spatial resolution analyses (50 μm) to be carried out. Monazite grains have a more variable grain size distribution, with an average of 60–70 μm. Their habit is irregular and they usually show rounded morphologies or broken grains. We carried out La, Th, Y, U and Nd compositional maps for every monazite grain in order to discover a compositional zonation that could be attributed to different growth events. Thorium zoning is the one that developed better and was taken into account to select the spots for isotopic analysis (Fig. 5), yet it never exceeds 30% of the grain. Several spots were analyzed in monazite crystals with the greatest compositional contrasts

Figure 5. (a) Monazite grain compositional maps in paragneiss with a 30% thorium variation. Location and spot numbers (46 and 47) are indicated, as well as the $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ age and error ($\pm 2\sigma$). (b) Chondrite-normalized REE patterns for the same monazite in panel (a).

Figure 6. CL images with the location of the analyzed spots for selected zircon grains.

to determine if they really represented different growth stages in the monazite grains.

Zircon grains from the paragneiss usually have scarce mineral inclusions and they can display a wide variety of morphologies, including irregular and subrounded shapes typical of metamorphic zircon, pristine elongated dipyrnidal prisms interpreted as igneous in origin and equigranular grains with abrasion signs with a probable detrital origin. Their length-to-width ratios vary between 3 : 1 and 2 : 1. Cathodoluminescence images (Fig. 6) are useful to relate the crystallization of parts of zircon crystals to specific igneous, metamorphic or deformational events (Corfu et al., 2003; Nasdala et al., 2003; Zeck et al., 2004). It is common to image a homogeneous xenocrystic core in zircon grains and even a less luminescent mantle in some grains (grain

numbers 5, 6). The core aspect is mainly rounded, with irregular or angular shapes. In most of the zircon grains, the internal parts of the grains display an oscillatory zoning (grain numbers 33, 71), with different thickness, although in some cases, this zoning is faint (grain number 26). There are several grains with sector zones (grain numbers 26, 27) parallel to the zircon *c* axis (Watson and Yan Liang, 1995) and even one case of soccer-ball zoning (grain number 82). The zoning usually appears to be partially truncated and surrounded by a discontinuous poorly luminescent rim (grain numbers 20, 79).

3.4 Analytical techniques

U/Th–Pb, REE and Hf analyses of zircon, titanite and monazite were carried out using the laser ablation split stream (LASS) at the University of California at Santa Barbara (UCSB). The samples were ablated using a Photon Machines 193 nm ArF excimer ultraviolet laser with a HelEx ablation cell coupled to a Nu Instruments Plasma high-resolution multi-collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (MC-ICP-MS) and either a Nu Instruments AttoM high-resolution single-collector ICP or an Agilent 7700S quadrupole ICP-MS (Kylander-Clark et al., 2013). This installation allows the simultaneous isotopic and compositional (REE) analysis to be carried out. The laser spot diameter was 20 μm for zircon, 7–10 μm for monazite (Kořler et al., 2001) and 50 μm for titanite (Stearns et al., 2016), resulting in pit depths between 6 μm for monazite and 30 μm for titanite. The laser has a fluence of $\sim 1 \text{ J cm}^{-2}$ and was fired twice to remove common Pb from the sample surface. This material was allowed to wash out for 15 s, prior to the material being ablated at 3 Hz for 20 s for analysis. On the ICP-MS, the masses $^{204}\text{Pb} + \text{Hg}$, ^{206}Pb , ^{207}Pb and ^{208}Pb were measured using ion counters, and the masses ^{232}Th and ^{238}U were measured using Faraday detectors.

The U/Th–Pb standardization for monazite was carried out using sample 44069 (Aleinikoff et al., 2006) as the pri-

primary reference material (RM), whereas the Bananeira sample was employed as primary RM for trace element corrections (Kylander-Clark et al., 2013; Palin et al., 2013). Additionally, FC-1 (Horstwood et al., 2003), Trebilcock (Tomaschak et al., 1996) and Bananeira were also used as secondary monazite RM, allowing $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages to be within 2 % of their accepted values. U–Pb proportions in titanite were corrected using Bear Laken (Aleinikoff et al., 2007) and Y1710C5 (Spencer et al., 2013) as RM. Overall, the 91500 sample (Wieldenbeck et al., 1995) and GJI (Jackson et al., 2004) were used as RM for zircon, both for isotopic composition and trace element calibrations. Radiogenic lead versus common lead ($^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$) measurements require up to 2 % additional external error attributable either to variation count statistics, or ablation signal stability (Spencer et al., 2013; Hacker et al., 2015b). These external errors were incorporated into the data in the experiments.

The Iolite plug-in version 2.5 (Paton et al., 2011) from the Wavemetrics Igor Pro software was used to improve and reduce the analyses (Hacker et al., 2015). The isotopic ratios $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ and $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ for each analysis were plotted on Tera–Wasserburg diagrams (Tera and Wasserburg, 1972) using Isoplot and Topsoil programs (Ludwig, 2012; Zeringue et al., 2014). All date uncertainties are reported at the 95 % confidence interval, assuming a Gaussian distribution of measurement errors. Zircon, titanite and monazite REE analyses were normalized against the McDonough and Sun (1995) chondrite values.

4 Results

4.1 Titanite (amphibolite, upper tectonic slice)

Overall, 51 titanite analyses were projected onto a Tera–Wasserburg concordia plot (Fig. 7a). After a preliminary evaluation, 12 analyses were rejected due to either high common Pb or high discordance ($> 10\%$) and were considered no further (Table 1). The remaining analyses define a Pb/U semi-total isochron between the common or initial Pb (^{207}Pb) and radiogenic Pb (^{206}Pb) (Ludwig, 1998). The good fit of the isochron confirms the chemical homogeneity of the data (Stearns et al., 2016) and it intercepts the concordia at 364.8 ± 4.5 Ma (2σ). Titanite chondrite-normalized REE analyses are detailed in Table 1 and are shown in Fig. 7b. Titanite REE patterns are convex upwards, relatively flat, with slight LREE depletions versus HREE with respect to chondrite. They generally lack a europium anomaly (Eu^*), but some analyses show a non-distinctive positive or negative anomaly.

4.2 Monazite (paragneiss, middle tectonic slice)

For monazite U/Th—Pb geochronology, we used the thorium zoning in monazite grains to select the analytic spots. As shown in Fig. 5, there are no significant age differences

between spots or zones with different Th chemical concentrations in a single grain. The obtained REE patterns are also very similar, and the mismatch at the HREE is probably due to either uncertainties in measurement because of the lower counts or interference effects of intermediate rare-earth oxides (Holder et al., 2015).

Data from 76 U/Th—Pb monazite analyses are shown in Table 2 and displayed using a Tera–Wasserburg concordia plot (Fig. 8a). Four of these analyses, not related to chemical zoning, were discarded due to common Pb loss and were considered no further. The remaining analyses form a single population (mean square of weighted deviation; $\text{MSWD} = 0.48$) centered on a concordia age of 382.5 ± 1.0 Ma (2σ). Monazite geochemistry is shown in Fig. 8b. REE patterns analyzed show an LREE enrichment, HREE depletion and negative Y anomalies with respect to chondrite with little variation within or between samples.

4.3 U–Pb zircon (paragneiss, middle tectonic slice)

Overall, 83 analyses were performed on 80 zircon grains from the Sobrado paragneiss (Table 3). In a preliminary assessment of the data, two analyses were rejected due to analytical errors (grain numbers 8 and 36). Additionally, 23 analyses yielded a discordance higher than 10 % and will not be further considered. The remaining 58 zircon analyses are shown on a Wetherill concordia plot (Fig. 9a). The $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ ages older than 1000 Ma are presented in a probability density plot (Fig. 9b). Most of the old ages are distributed between 1880 and 2200 Ma, with two peaks at 2030 and 2100 Ma. Three ages are older, around 2600 Ma, and there are also two analyses around 1300 Ma. The $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages younger than 1000 Ma are plotted on a Tera–Wasserburg concordia plot (Fig. 10a) and a probability density plot (Fig. 10b). The data are continuously distributed between 589 and 380 Ma and attending to their CL texture, ages from 589 to 510 Ma are obtained mainly from internal areas with oscillatory or sector zoning (e.g., 33, 27 and 62; see Fig. 6), whereas ages from 510 to 380 Ma correspond to discordant rims that have homogeneous CL signal, except for some grains (e.g., 10, 11 and 26; see Fig. 6) that are cores with oscillatory or sector zoning.

4.4 REE zircon (paragneiss, middle tectonic slice)

The chondrite-normalized REE patterns of the zircons with ages older than 600 Ma are shown in Fig. 11. In general, this group has REE patterns with a pronounced fractionation from light to heavy REE and two anomalies in Ce (positive) and in Eu (negative). There are only three analyses that diverge from this trend and show a flat HREE pattern.

For the younger analyses, the chondrite-normalized REE patterns have different features depending on the age (Fig. 12). The oldest ages (589–510 Ma) show a tight HREE fractionation, variable Eu anomaly, and a pronounced Ce

Table 1. U–Th–Pb and REE titanite_McD_S.

Spot	²³⁸ U/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁸ Pb/ ²³² Th	U (ppm)	Th(ppm)	La (ppm)	Ce (ppm)	Pr (ppm)	Nd (ppm)	Sm (ppm)	Eu (ppm)	Gd (ppm)	Tb (ppm)	Dy (ppm)	Ho (ppm)	Er (ppm)	Tm (ppm)	Yb (ppm)	Lu (ppm)	
1	15.59 ± 0.35	0.1279 ± 0.0032	0.02292 ± 0.00053	7.42	16.57	751	1052	1182	1096	1012	1012	1012	818	681	635	590	521	423.1	405	363.4
2	13.37 ± 0.66	0.1625 ± 0.0004	0.0258 ± 0.00074	8.22	16.73	701	946	1107	1085	1128	904	1128	889	762	661	584	584	333.6	324	232.9
3	13.74 ± 0.36	0.2123 ± 0.00056	0.03513 ± 0.00101	4.16	7.44	327	424	520	538	588	588	574	559	522	538	532	411.7	465	392.7	
4	13.85 ± 0.36	0.1694 ± 0.00045	0.0514 ± 0.00298	4.3	2.47	116	188	275	318	484	519	503	471	419	408	408	365	278.9	299	230.5
5	13.7 ± 0.41	0.2426 ± 0.0067	0.0545 ± 0.00376	2.71	2.35	109	209	297	383	511	561	458	437	422	416	386	287.9	315	261.4	
6	14.2 ± 0.4	0.1864 ± 0.0058	0.0318 ± 0.00119	3.16	4.74	225	300	369	409	547	671	561	539	495	526	511	393.5	448	383.7	
7	12.06 ± 0.52	0.2955 ± 0.0111	0.15 ± 0.18002	2	1.46	68	111	153	199	314	382	329	361	373	394	399	318.6	340	290.7	
8	14.52 ± 0.33	0.1863 ± 0.0005	0.03051 ± 0.00091	4.86	7.93	394	574	681	705	762	813	685	648	589	608	579	436.8	504	417.1	
9	15.11 ± 0.35	0.131 ± 0.0037	0.02719 ± 0.00074	6.55	10.39	471	692	733	803	861	828	714	679	636	703	693	565.6	650	561	
10	12.55 ± 0.37	0.2611 ± 0.0083	0.144 ± 0.0401	2.35	0.96	45	90	152	217	359	442	328	329	300	291	304	252.6	290	245.5	
11	15.48 ± 0.35	0.1264 ± 0.0034	0.0334 ± 0.00137	8.13	6.22	350	654	938	1120	1201	1107	1045	928	902	890	901	659.9	711	586.6	
12	7.3 ± 1.08	0.471 ± 0.0153	0.072 ± 0.09601	0.61	0.32	15	27	42	67	134	140	162	189	215	233	264	248.2	287	232.1	
13	10.02 ± 0.47	0.4211 ± 0.0111	0.112 ± 0.09503	1.2	0.69	31	61	98	139	244	209	230	214	156	108	93	78.5	80	72.8	
14	9.66 ± 0.47	0.387 ± 0.0135	0.22 ± 0.17006	1.09	0.56	29	55	79	96	159	197	160	181	200	213	249	230.4	296	242.7	
15	15.99 ± 0.32	0.191 ± 0.0046	0.03377 ± 0.00107	4.58	6.1	184	317	421	512	599	485	518	467	433	401	374	319.8	306	236.2	
16	14.41 ± 0.41	0.1672 ± 0.0063	0.0315 ± 0.00144	4.02	5.44	216	359	421	492	642	501	609	609	590	549	545	471.3	464	395.9	
17	14.94 ± 0.36	0.1761 ± 0.0048	0.13 ± 0.03609	4.38	0.71	43	108	170	239	404	460	433	485	572	540	536	488.3	420	339	
18	7.35 ± 0.77	0.549 ± 0.0155	-0.08 ± -0.14001	0.55	0.3	18	26	36	42	68	68	77	92	122	141	181	210.9	230	204.5	
19	15.96 ± 0.36	0.1397 ± 0.0034	0.0271 ± 0.00071	8.1	9.22	414	520	541	580	692	609	652	624	708	579	591	630.8	507	405.7	
20	15.04 ± 0.33	0.1649 ± 0.0049	0.03031 ± 0.00096	6.39	8.79	293	426	468	522	543	499	482	455	514	419	438	446.6	412	321.1	
21	11.9 ± 0.34	0.3127 ± 0.0079	0.37 ± 0.22012	2.91	0.4	48	108	185	276	507	426	527	465	385	218	153	120.2	80	59.3	
22	14.41 ± 0.34	0.194 ± 0.0054	0.0514 ± 0.00216	5.29	3.73	255	465	598	716	889	794	766	709	817	603	595	629.1	472	382.1	
23	14.18 ± 0.37	0.1682 ± 0.0046	0.098 ± 0.01612	4.77	1.43	102	228	355	458	710	718	687	604	671	488	476	449.4	344	258.5	
24	15.92 ± 0.35	0.1147 ± 0.0003	0.02388 ± 0.00057	10.78	13.2	468	695	829	915	901	1052	731	604	620	458	442	428.3	323	278	
25	7.63 ± 0.83	0.512 ± 0.015	-0.03 ± -0.49	0.68	0.14	9	21	37	56	110	157	147	157	209	182	211	270.4	234	214.2	
26	12.27 ± 0.5	0.32 ± 0.0119	0.0577 ± 0.00542	1.68	2.17	93	148	203	243	286	325	275	274	313	271	307	349	312	285.4	
27	14.67 ± 0.35	0.1937 ± 0.0048	0.03279 ± 0.00098	4.67	6.77	354	560	653	700	703	639	652	551	557	401	347	332.8	248	162.6	
28	15.2 ± 0.46	0.1543 ± 0.0069	0.0335 ± 0.00183	4.88	4.43	174	326	463	554	642	542	542	593	512	581	487	521.1	496	453.7	
29	14.56 ± 0.31	0.112 ± 0.0029	0.02158 ± 0.00049	11.71	22.45	495	625	696	722	728	886	653	584	642	562	575	536	444	363	
30	10.92 ± 0.38	0.3387 ± 0.0094	0.0584 ± 0.00378	1.54	2.51	111	129	147	168	229	267	270	312	375	364	431	455.9	451	411	
31	10.64 ± 0.67	0.368 ± 0.0132	0.122 ± 0.03409	1.07	0.81	29	58	84	114	158	173	195	184	230	228	262	283	270	259.3	
32	9.39 ± 0.5	0.443 ± 0.0141	-0.02 ± -0.12	0.9	0.58	22	42	61	81	130	179	152	162	207	205	242	246.2	289	248.8	
33	10.49 ± 0.65	0.3651 ± 0.0111	0.095 ± 0.00969	1.13	1.22	55	82	100	120	149	189	163	162	203	196	229	210.5	247	236.6	
34	15.19 ± 0.35	0.1501 ± 0.0004	0.042 ± 0.00163	5.56	3.48	235	434	593	696	705	801	639	537	517	454	488	390.3	419	399.2	
35	14.53 ± 0.41	0.1866 ± 0.0067	0.0339 ± 0.00129	3.69	4.89	172	263	322	383	457	471	483	465	516	482	494	401.6	464	401.2	
36	14.66 ± 0.36	0.1785 ± 0.0047	0.0584 ± 0.00378	4.36	2.21	111	252	399	514	703	588	649	544	524	463	461	351.8	391	368.3	
37	16.03 ± 0.34	0.1359 ± 0.0032	0.0472 ± 0.0023	8.41	3.38	281	400	473	503	493	611	443	355	366	321	320	264.8	297	287.8	
38	10.52 ± 0.48	0.3435 ± 0.0113	0.144 ± 0.06906	1.28	0.55	22	40	63	93	172	221	236	293	370	352	385	304	348	308.1	
39	8.65 ± 0.61	0.496 ± 0.0164	0 ± 0	0.66	0.24	9	17	29	37	85	123	126	158	215	232	284	215.8	278	267.9	
40	15.85 ± 0.34	0.116 ± 0.0028	0.02681 ± 0.00008	7.59	7.2	348	566	735	869	950	1151	862	731	739	619	632	420.2	530	460.6	
41	11.89 ± 0.31	0.1654 ± 0.0046	0.06 ± 0.14001	2.54	0.09	16	60	148	259	580	512	585	518	511	425	428	291.9	411	362.2	
42	9.82 ± 0.57	0.4175 ± 0.0124	0.138 ± 0.08205	0.95	0.79	71	99	105	109	98	210	94	87	100	89	104	74.5	115	122	
43	15.67 ± 0.34	0.1411 ± 0.0037	0.02576 ± 0.00068	6.21	10.38	640	799	852	832	803	913	671	607	625	520	493	319.8	397	362.2	
44	11.01 ± 0.57	0.3661 ± 0.0111	0.11 ± 0.14002	1.2	0.86	34	57	75	99	154	196	174	218	270	274	316	272.5	369	345.9	
45	7.67 ± 0.6	0.484 ± 0.0139	0.04 ± 0.25	0.57	0.33	20	33	42	58	105	123	136	150	193	200	221	204	263	280.5	
46	13.25 ± 0.39	0.2117 ± 0.0071	0.0379 ± 0.00242	2.61	4.41	228	284	304	324	395	455	384	348	358	302	284	195.5	227	204.9	
47	10.78 ± 0.54	0.2924 ± 0.0105	0.133 ± 0.07405	1.66	0.79	37	79	118	165	255	304	277	309	340	313	321	253.8	305	288.2	
48	6.94 ± 0.74	0.511 ± 0.0158	0.0745 ± 0.0057	0.64	1.89	173	290	339	376	356	230	303	269	273	260	255	186.6	217	199.2	
49	15.64 ± 0.33	0.1197 ± 0.0028	0.03214 ± 0.0001	10.32	7.5	521	772	845	886	937	1130	845	676	683	551	478	336	339	299.2	
50	10.66 ± 0.43	0.3635 ± 0.0094	0.0697 ± 0.00481	1.77	2.45	197	218	213	235	245	269	259	261	294	258	279	210.9	246	236.6	
51	7.32 ± 0.55	0.569 ± 0.0158	0.0894 ± 0.0082	0.7	1.76	183	217	191	182	143	85	107	102	102	101	107	92.3	114	118.7	

Table 2. U-Th-Pb and REE monazite_McD_S.

Spot	$^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$	$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$	$^{208}\text{Pb}/^{232}\text{Th}$	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	Pa (ppm)	Ce (ppm)	Pr (ppm)	Nd (ppm)	Sm (ppm)	Eu (ppm)	Gd (ppm)	Tb (ppm)	Dy (ppm)	Y (ppm)	Ho (ppm)	Er (ppm)	Tm (ppm)	Yb (ppm)	Lu (ppm)
1	16.29 ± 0.35	0.0543 ± 0.0013	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1640	26.200	554.450	433.931	346.302	243.982	98.243	12.131	10.899	4439	992	245	273	170	32.4	20	3.3
2	16.28 ± 0.35	0.0543 ± 0.0013	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1830	29.300	537.904	437.194	352.371	243.451	94.524	13.286	10.740	4490	1081	252	322	101	27.5	25	0.0
3	16.29 ± 0.38	0.0544 ± 0.0013	0.0190 ± 0.0004	2300	29.500	519.409	420.881	346.938	230.109	107.306	12.431	12.869	5319	1083	282	374	100	24.8	8	24.8
4	16.30 ± 0.38	0.0544 ± 0.0013	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1434	34.200	563.113	425.716	323.276	222.652	85.270	11.474	18.345	4266	898	192	251	118	46.6	14	12.2
5	16.09 ± 0.35	0.0541 ± 0.0013	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1805	35.400	524.651	409.462	335.448	197.587	92.868	11.385	19.899	4197	1045	179	260	143	38.1	10	5.0
6	16.27 ± 0.36	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	1660	25.900	554.505	442.088	338.302	230.704	96.622	11.794	19.045	4634	890	227	291	184	44.5	20	5.7
7	16.15 ± 0.36	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	2170	44.100	579.524	447.194	359.914	248.795	95.638	12.647	18.965	4072	1045	248	306	172	46.6	10	5.7
8	16.22 ± 0.37	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	2130	44.100	567.311	422.512	340.517	248.295	90.608	12.451	17.789	3958	902	232	286	182	42.1	12	8.1
9	16.28 ± 0.38	0.0549 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1680	27.900	526.160	433.563	357.789	242.451	93.919	12.664	17.969	3988	947	210	264	143	25.6	6	25.6
10	16.38 ± 0.37	0.0547 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1680	27.900	526.160	433.563	357.789	242.451	93.919	12.664	17.969	3988	947	210	264	143	25.6	6	25.6
11	16.29 ± 0.37	0.0547 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	2280	35.700	555.274	433.931	363.621	258.923	95.270	12.000	19.226	4452	996	221	321	181	44.1	17	7.0
12	16.29 ± 0.37	0.0547 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	2280	35.700	555.274	433.931	363.621	258.923	95.270	12.000	19.226	4452	996	221	321	181	44.1	17	7.0
13	16.28 ± 0.38	0.0548 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	2230	42.200	540.928	411.093	349.138	248.827	94.662	12.012	18.643	4351	976	218	282	138	36.0	13	0.0
14	16.28 ± 0.38	0.0548 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	2060	41.000	564.135	438.825	378.233	262.888	103.514	13.268	22.412	5123	1085	209	335	162	25.1	16	11.8
15	16.31 ± 0.39	0.0545 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	2020	29.600	535.865	450.243	391.164	240.888	103.514	12.968	22.412	5123	1085	209	335	162	25.1	16	11.8
16	16.23 ± 0.36	0.0544 ± 0.0012	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1714	31.400	565.401	429.038	366.379	241.357	96.689	10.954	19.196	4452	1004	218	291	177	25.5	17	8.9
17	16.40 ± 0.36	0.0546 ± 0.0012	0.0191 ± 0.0004	2260	37.500	580.391	464.927	376.078	262.363	100.600	12.286	18.894	4654	1084	218	308	168	48.2	17	3.3
18	16.22 ± 0.38	0.0538 ± 0.0013	0.0194 ± 0.0004	1662	30.800	564.927	427.406	363.621	240.420	101.419	12.593	20.050	4399	1024	217	253	161	34.0	16	4.8
19	16.25 ± 0.38	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1600	31.200	618.143	442.088	383.621	248.919	101.351	12.611	18.695	4197	1024	217	253	161	34.0	16	4.8
20	16.11 ± 0.35	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	2190	34.200	567.922	443.719	365.302	248.672	100.554	12.913	19.497	4398	1065	208	288	102	28.8	30	30.8
21	16.17 ± 0.35	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1804	38.200	560.338	448.613	383.621	248.672	97.230	12.647	16.281	4019	1110	246	264	110	68.0	19	11.0
22	16.08 ± 0.35	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	2800	38.200	560.338	448.613	383.621	248.672	97.230	12.647	16.281	4019	1110	246	264	110	68.0	19	11.0
23	16.08 ± 0.35	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	2800	38.200	560.338	448.613	383.621	248.672	97.230	12.647	16.281	4019	1110	246	264	110	68.0	19	11.0
24	16.08 ± 0.35	0.0543 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1704	84.000	564.472	417.618	339.914	238.731	97.635	12.654	16.935	4329	1110	246	264	110	68.0	19	11.0
25	16.37 ± 0.39	0.0546 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	1650	57.800	564.572	422.512	364.991	240.453	97.635	12.700	17.256	4488	963	249	306	184	56.3	8	14.6
26	16.43 ± 0.38	0.0550 ± 0.0013	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1663	32.900	575.949	432.300	354.526	240.453	100.608	13.240	19.347	4958	1167	273	306	177	73.3	17	7.3
27	16.32 ± 0.39	0.0549 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	2000	32.900	582.700	442.512	363.147	240.453	118.243	15.062	25.025	6648	1167	273	306	177	73.3	17	7.3
28	16.38 ± 0.38	0.0538 ± 0.0011	0.0194 ± 0.0004	3680	28.300	582.700	442.512	363.147	240.453	118.243	15.062	25.025	6648	1167	273	306	177	73.3	17	7.3
29	16.58 ± 0.35	0.0539 ± 0.0011	0.0190 ± 0.0004	3050	32.100	551.899	432.300	375.000	240.304	118.243	14.512	24.171	6227	1451	342	443	213	45.7	25	16.7
30	16.27 ± 0.38	0.0546 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	1822	27.600	562.447	440.557	375.000	240.304	118.243	14.512	24.171	6227	1451	342	443	213	45.7	25	16.7
31	16.68 ± 0.40	0.0544 ± 0.0013	0.0191 ± 0.0004	1936	28.200	570.424	437.194	350.216	232.604	104.054	13.604	21.156	5235	1102	340	352	191	30.4	24	16.7
32	16.68 ± 0.40	0.0544 ± 0.0013	0.0191 ± 0.0004	1936	28.200	570.424	437.194	350.216	232.604	104.054	13.604	21.156	5235	1102	340	352	191	30.4	24	16.7
33	16.36 ± 0.37	0.0541 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	2220	30.500	556.540	414.356	369.613	248.359	102.703	13.144	18.191	4834	1041	300	291	168	47.8	18	3.3
34	16.36 ± 0.37	0.0541 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	2220	30.500	556.540	414.356	369.613	248.359	102.703	13.144	18.191	4834	1041	300	291	168	47.8	18	3.3
35	16.39 ± 0.41	0.0544 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	2480	30.300	587.342	407.830	355.603	255.580	100.338	13.197	20.442	4799	1043	248	343	201	39.3	16	16.4
36	16.31 ± 0.36	0.0544 ± 0.0013	0.0191 ± 0.0004	2100	43.900	580.931	402.936	367.457	247.964	113.446	14.725	24.372	6427	1439	341	452	231	64.4	16	24.8
37	16.34 ± 0.44	0.0552 ± 0.0013	0.0191 ± 0.0004	2240	42.200	582.700	435.563	365.302	247.964	100.811	13.002	21.809	5312	1150	239	295	179	33.2	35	9.3
38	16.54 ± 0.38	0.0543 ± 0.0013	0.0191 ± 0.0004	1419	31.800	571.308	414.356	348.147	247.964	97.104	11.829	18.543	4645	1008	214	286	162	49.4	24	8.5
39	16.39 ± 0.40	0.0550 ± 0.0014	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1930	31.600	565.823	443.719	350.216	240.234	97.754	12.504	19.598	4933	1077	222	267	157	51.8	17	20.7
40	16.44 ± 0.39	0.0542 ± 0.0013	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1690	40.600	562.447	435.563	387.931	242.363	85.405	11.332	18.342	4571	1045	231	333	178	41.3	18	13.4
41	16.57 ± 0.38	0.0548 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1655	34.400	562.447	435.563	387.931	242.363	85.405	11.332	18.342	4571	1045	231	333	178	41.3	18	13.4
42	16.57 ± 0.38	0.0548 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1655	34.400	562.447	435.563	387.931	242.363	85.405	11.332	18.342	4571	1045	231	333	178	41.3	18	13.4
43	16.26 ± 0.37	0.0545 ± 0.0013	0.0194 ± 0.0004	2260	37.200	569.198	432.300	363.621	247.964	100.728	12.771	18.291	4654	1037	231	311	164	21.5	16	16.4
44	16.26 ± 0.37	0.0545 ± 0.0013	0.0194 ± 0.0004	2260	37.200	569.198	432.300	363.621	247.964	100.728	12.771	18.291	4654	1037	231	311	164	21.5	16	16.4
45	16.22 ± 0.37	0.0540 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1674	44.700	538.992	414.356	329.741	239.168	87.365	11.812	18.342	4820	1057	245	336	202	49.4	14	0.0
46	16.22 ± 0.37	0.0540 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1674	44.700	538.992	414.356	329.741	239.168	87.365	11.812	18.342	4820	1057	245	336	202	49.4	14	0.0
47	16.57 ± 0.41	0.0539 ± 0.0013	0.0190 ± 0.0004	1674	30.300	538.992	402.936	328.664	239.168	87.365	11.812	18.342	4820	1057	245	336	202	49.4	14	0.0
48	16.44 ± 0.42	0.0535 ± 0.0012	0.0192 ± 0.0004	1789	31.400	540.928	446.982	351.293	240.336	94.054	12.721	18.595	5308	1000	262	311	180	57.5	19	8.1
49	16.21 ± 0.37	0.0533 ± 0.0013	0.0194 ± 0.0004	1810	33.800	570.644	446.982	351.293	240.336	94.054	12.721	18.595	5308	1000	262	311	180	57.5	19	8.1
50	16.40 ± 0.37	0.0543 ± 0.0013	0.0194 ± 0.0004	1810	33.800	570.644	446.982	351.293	240.336	94.054	12.721	18.595	5308	1000	262	311	180	57.5	19	8.1
51	16.66 ± 0.40	0.0544 ± 0.0012	0.0194 ± 0.0004	4730	31.600	561.603	411.093	340.517	242.582	99.459	12.824	21.899	5125	1264	283	308	190	24.7	8	2.4
52																				

Table 3. U–Th–Pb zircon sorted by age.

Spot	Location	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	Th/U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	2σ	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	2σ	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	2σ	ρ	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U Age (Ma)	2σ	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U Age (Ma)	2σ	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb Age (Ma)	2σ	Probability of concordance
3	Core	690	223	0.32	10.760	0.242	0.423	0.0093	0.184	0.004	-0.05	2502	9	2272	18	2691	6	0.91
72		495	22	0.04	10.230	0.273	0.421	0.0111	0.174	0.004	0.06	2455	16	2264	33	2596	6	0.92
82	Rim	280	136	0.48	9.840	0.281	0.403	0.0112	0.177	0.004	-0.36	2418	19	2183	36	2625	5	0.90
80		46	34	0.74	6.460	0.176	0.364	0.0095	0.128	0.003	-0.06	2039	17	1998	29	2065	8	0.98
40		62	40	0.64	6.390	0.182	0.358	0.0097	0.130	0.003	-0.31	2030	18	1974	31	2095	9	0.97
37		151	53	0.35	6.426	0.151	0.358	0.0082	0.131	0.003	-0.19	2035	11	1972	19	2107	7	0.97
44		100	109	1.09	6.100	0.193	0.356	0.0108	0.124	0.003	-0.14	1989	21	1960	38	2020	8	0.99
2		444	141	0.32	8.210	0.198	0.355	0.0082	0.168	0.003	-0.31	2256	12	1958	19	2542	4	0.87
5		70	102	1.47	5.854	0.150	0.342	0.0090	0.125	0.003	0.01	1957	15	1895	28	2035	9	0.97
28		878	74	0.08	7.890	0.218	0.334	0.0090	0.173	0.004	-0.07	2218	18	1858	30	2584	10	0.84
48		28	15	0.53	6.030	0.251	0.334	0.0137	0.130	0.003	-0.12	1976	32	1856	58	2098	15	0.94
32		101	49	0.49	5.867	0.153	0.333	0.0085	0.129	0.003	0.18	1956	14	1853	26	2080	10	0.95
18		49	19	0.38	5.977	0.155	0.321	0.0083	0.137	0.003	0.03	1975	16	1799	23	2184	12	0.91
4		677	299	0.44	5.659	0.146	0.316	0.0080	0.130	0.003	-0.30	1924	14	1767	24	2103	5	0.92
83		48	22	0.47	5.510	0.163	0.314	0.0093	0.127	0.003	0.10	1906	20	1762	34	2056	15	0.93
39		125	113	0.90	5.190	0.144	0.309	0.0082	0.122	0.003	-0.39	1849	17	1737	27	1987	9	0.94
49		403	115	0.29	6.840	0.196	0.307	0.0083	0.161	0.003	-0.10	2090	18	1732	29	2466	9	0.83
35		182	124	0.68	5.660	0.158	0.298	0.0078	0.138	0.003	-0.22	1924	17	1683	25	2204	13	0.87
51		304	97	0.32	5.366	0.145	0.297	0.0079	0.131	0.003	-0.13	1878	16	1676	26	2111	5	0.89
66		693	223	0.32	6.470	0.176	0.295	0.0079	0.158	0.003	-0.11	2041	17	1664	26	2433	5	0.82
21		587	251	0.43	5.019	0.124	0.294	0.0070	0.125	0.003	-0.25	1824	12	1663	19	2028	5	0.91
16		118	107	0.91	5.043	0.126	0.294	0.0071	0.125	0.003	-0.23	1826	13	1660	20	2032	9	0.91
65		407	6	0.02	4.481	0.111	0.270	0.0067	0.120	0.002	0.15	1730	11	1539	20	1956	5	0.89
1		52	36	0.70	4.496	0.129	0.266	0.0072	0.122	0.003	-0.26	1729	17	1524	24	1995	14	0.88
22		128	32	0.25	4.144	0.103	0.266	0.0065	0.115	0.002	-0.13	1663	12	1519	19	1881	10	0.91
24		166	71	0.43	4.140	0.154	0.260	0.0086	0.117	0.002	-0.72	1660	25	1490	35	1910	12	0.90
54		66	43	0.64	4.218	0.118	0.253	0.0070	0.121	0.003	-0.09	1677	16	1452	25	1975	13	0.87
81		80	47	0.59	4.091	0.115	0.246	0.0068	0.120	0.003	0.00	1652	16	1417	24	1960	12	0.86
23		71	51	0.71	4.060	0.162	0.244	0.0080	0.121	0.003	-0.50	1650	29	1406	33	1979	15	0.85
31		41	17	0.41	3.840	0.134	0.236	0.0072	0.118	0.003	-0.29	1600	23	1367	28	1931	16	0.85
38		48	27	0.56	2.564	0.088	0.214	0.0072	0.087	0.002	0.00	1289	20	1251	31	1372	20	0.97
58		463	39	0.08	3.354	0.099	0.210	0.0060	0.116	0.002	-0.39	1496	18	1228	23	1903	10	0.82
46		275	126	0.46	2.377	0.068	0.208	0.0059	0.082	0.002	-0.19	1235	15	1219	22	1252	8	0.99
50		321	114	0.35	3.216	0.091	0.205	0.0059	0.115	0.002	-0.13	1463	16	1202	23	1876	8	0.82
9		53	45	0.84	2.485	0.076	0.170	0.0049	0.106	0.002	0.04	1267	17	1011	20	1724	17	0.80
41		36	16	0.45	2.302	0.077	0.156	0.0052	0.107	0.003	0.07	1211	19	935	23	1754	23	0.77
45		65	29	0.45	2.113	0.072	0.153	0.0047	0.100	0.002	-0.17	1152	19	919	20	1620	18	0.80
30		270	29	0.11	1.994	0.083	0.146	0.0049	0.099	0.002	-0.73	1111	25	878	22	1607	20	0.79
78		157	40	0.26	1.241	0.040	0.111	0.0031	0.081	0.002	-0.30	818	14	677	13	1215	19	0.83
77		397	18	0.05	1.284	0.042	0.111	0.0033	0.084	0.002	-0.40	838	15	675	14	1287	10	0.81
73		238	34	0.14	1.054	0.042	0.097	0.0028	0.077	0.002	-0.57	730	17	597	12	1121	24	0.82
19		224	185	0.83	0.775	0.020	0.096	0.0024	0.060	0.001	0.00	582	8	589	9	585	15	1.01
14		264	120	0.45	0.744	0.020	0.092	0.0024	0.059	0.001	0.06	564	8	567	10	564	18	1.00
69		39	33	0.84	0.687	0.022	0.089	0.0022	0.056	0.001	0.07	531	10	552	8	466	40	1.04
64		409	196	0.48	0.708	0.019	0.089	0.0021	0.058	0.001	0.02	544	8	549	7	531	15	1.01
56		37	66	1.77	0.693	0.026	0.089	0.0025	0.057	0.002	-0.24	534	13	548	10	494	49	1.02
52		113	49	0.44	0.720	0.022	0.088	0.0023	0.060	0.001	0.08	550	9	546	9	591	23	0.99
43		119	68	0.57	0.716	0.022	0.088	0.0025	0.059	0.001	-0.04	548	10	544	11	567	22	0.99
60		148	95	0.64	0.708	0.019	0.087	0.0021	0.059	0.001	0.17	545	8	540	7	559	24	0.99
57		119	117	0.99	0.709	0.019	0.086	0.0024	0.059	0.001	0.20	544	7	532	10	574	24	0.98
62	456	176	0.39	0.691	0.018	0.086	0.0022	0.058	0.001	-0.01	535	8	532	8	539	12	1.00	
27	61	45	0.74	0.681	0.023	0.086	0.0025	0.058	0.002	0.21	527	11	532	11	522	39	1.01	
68	66	47	0.71	0.695	0.023	0.086	0.0023	0.058	0.001	0.04	535	11	531	9	558	33	0.99	
42	136	114	0.84	0.692	0.020	0.086	0.0023	0.059	0.001	-0.12	534	9	530	9	551	24	0.99	
13	184	64	0.35	0.674	0.017	0.085	0.0020	0.058	0.001	0.29	523	7	526	7	523	24	1.01	
6	1215	931	0.77	0.694	0.016	0.085	0.0019	0.060	0.001	0.09	535	5	524	5	588	9	0.98	
55	215	71	0.33	0.681	0.020	0.085	0.0021	0.058	0.001	-0.21	527	9	523	8	549	16	0.99	
33	82	69	0.84	0.667	0.019	0.085	0.0025	0.058	0.001	0.10	519	9	523	10	512	26	1.01	
12	74	55	0.75	0.656	0.018	0.084	0.0020	0.057	0.002	0.12	512	8	520	6	468	40	1.02	
74	48	38	0.78	0.675	0.021	0.084	0.0023	0.058	0.002	-0.04	524	10	519	9	520	42	0.99	
34	296	229	0.77	0.655	0.017	0.083	0.0020	0.057	0.001	0.04	512	7	511	7	498	16	1.00	
63	122	804	6.59	0.674	0.021	0.082	0.0022	0.059	0.001	-0.03	523	10	510	8	577	29	0.97	
47	173	2	0.01	0.637	0.018	0.081	0.0019	0.058	0.001	-0.03	500	8	502	6	522	27	1.00	
61	Rim	166	25	0.15	0.636	0.016	0.081	0.0020	0.057	0.001	0.25	500	6	502	7	481	18	1.00
7	763	40	0.05	0.761	0.021	0.080	0.0021	0.069	0.001	-0.49	575	8	497	8	903	13	0.86	
67	394	4	0.01	0.635	0.015	0.079	0.0018	0.057	0.001	-0.15	499	5	493	6	500	14	0.99	
75	Rim	222	5	0.02	0.625	0.017	0.079	0.0021	0.056	0.001	0.14	493	8	492	8	453	22	1.00
11	601	358	0.60	0.615	0.016	0.078	0.0020	0.057	0.001	0.02	487	6	486	7	501	13	1.00	
26	125	103	0.82	0.604	0.015	0.078	0.0022	0.057	0.001	0.46	480	5	486	9	488	24	1.01	
71	301	7	0.02	0.602	0.016	0.078	0.0020	0.056	0.001	0.18	478	6	482	7	453	19	1.01	
29	261	11	0.04	0.685	0.082	0.077	0.0038	0.065	0.005	-0.90	524	46	479	21	740	140	0.90	
10	393	91	0.23	0.582	0.016	0.075	0.0021	0.056	0.001	-0.13	465	7	468	8	463	14	1.00	
53	253	8	0.03	0.581	0.017	0.075	0.0021	0.057	0.001	0.06	465	9	463	9	489	20	1.00	
70	378	7	0.02	0.572	0.015	0.074	0.0019	0.055	0.001	0.11	459	7	458	8	434	17		

Figure 7. (a) Tera–Wasserburg diagram showing distribution of analyzed titanite ($n = 51$) from Sobrado amphibolite (JBP-71-21). The rejected analyses are represented by gray ellipses. The ellipses represent the $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ and $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ errors ($\pm 2\sigma$). (b) Chondrite-normalized REE patterns for the same titanite.

Figure 8. (a) Tera–Wasserburg diagram showing distribution of analyzed monazite ($n = 76$) from Sobrado paragneiss (JBP-71-15). The rejected analyses are represented by gray ellipses. The ellipses represent the $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ and $^{238}\text{U}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ errors ($\pm 2\sigma$). (b) Chondrite-normalized REE patterns for the same monazite.

anomaly. The youngest ages (510–380 Ma) has a variable HREE slope, whereas the Eu anomaly is more regular, and the Ce anomaly is less marked.

When we plot age versus Hf, Yb/Gd and Eu/Ey* (Fig. 13a–c), the group of oldest ages (589–510 Ma) does not define any apparent trend. In sharp contrast, in the 500–380 Ma group it is remarkable not only the good correlation between age and composition but also the divergent evolution depending of the age (gray arrows). Hafnium, Yb/Gd and Eu/Ey* increase from 500 to ~ 430 Ma, while there is a striking decrease from ~ 420 to 380 Ma. Finally, we have used the U/Ce–Th graph proposed by Bacon et al. (2012) to discriminate between metamorphic and igneous zircon.

5 Discussion

5.1 Zircon geochronology: inheritance and age of magmatism

The presence of zircon inclusions shielded in garnets (e.g., Fig. 4e and g) is compatible with the preservation of magmatic, metamorphic or detrital inheritances during the syn-kinematic partial melting recorded in these rocks

(Benítez Pérez, 2017). As shown in Fig. 12, the majority of analyzed zircon grains older than 600 Ma have fractionated REE patterns that are characteristic of igneous zircon (Hoskin and Schaltegger, 2003; Whitehouse and Platt, 2003; Hanchar and Westrenen, 2007; Grimes et al., 2015). Only three analyses show a flat HREE pattern that can be related to the presence of garnet and interpreted as metamorphic zircon. The provenance of these zircon grains older than 600 Ma in the Sobrado migmatitic paragneiss (Fig. 9b), is probably similar to those reported in the intermediate-P units of NW Spain upper allochthons like the Betanzos unit (Fuenlabrada et al., 2010) and Cariño gneiss (Albert et al., 2015). We obtained two Mesoproterozoic ages, between 1.2 and 1.4 Ga. Similar ages are also found in the parautochthonous (Díez Fernández et al., 2012), in the basal allochthonous units (Díez Fernández et al., 2010) and, to a lesser extent, in the intermediate-P units of NW Spain (Albert et al., 2015). These inherited zircons, although scarce (Fernández-Suárez et al., 2003), likely have their origin in rocks derived from Saharan and Arabian–Nubian cratons, and presumably transported during the Cadomian orogeny (e.g., Martínez Catalán et al., 2004). Paleoproterozoic populations range from 1.8 to 2.2 Ga, clustered at 2.1 Ga, are also common in the al-

Figure 9. Concordia plot (a) including all zircon with concordance > 90% from sample JBP-71-15 (Sobrado migmatitic paragneiss) and (b) age histogram and probability density plot for ages older than 1000 Ma.

lochthonous complexes (Fernández-Suárez et al., 2003) and their origin likely involves materials generated or reworked during the Eburnean orogeny (e.g., Egal et al., 2002; Ennih and Liegeois, 2008) from the West African Craton (Peucat et al., 2005). Finally, the Archean population in the Sobrado paragneiss ranges from 2.5 to 2.8 Ga, and it is likely related to intrusive events in the western Reguibat Shield (Schofield et al., 2012) and the northern part of the West African Craton (Albert et al., 2015), with some reworking processes of juvenile rocks formed at approximately 3.0 Ga (Potrel et al., 1998).

Based on CL images, ages and zircon composition, we can determine that the youngest zircon with magmatic origin is grain number 34 (Fig. 6). The number obtained in this grain is comparable to other maximum depositional ages obtained from similar units in the NW Spain allochthonous complexes, such as the intermediate-P Betanzos uppermost unit (530–510 Ma; Fuenlabrada et al., 2010) and the intermediate-P Cariño uppermost unit (~ 510 Ma; Albert et al., 2015).

In order to get more insight into the meaning of the data younger than 600 Ma, we have plotted these ages versus the

Figure 10. Tera-Wasserburg diagram (a) for the analyses between 589 and 380 Ma, and (b) age histogram and probability density plot for the same ages.

Figure 11. Chondrite-normalized plots for inherited zircon older than 1000 Ma.

Th/U ratios (Fig. 14). Analyses that yielded ages between 589 and 510 Ma cluster together with Th/U values higher than 0.3. The REE patterns displayed in this cluster are consistent with a magmatic origin. In the age versus Hf Yb/Gd and Eu/Eu* plots for this group (Fig. 13a–c), the absence of a trend suggests that the different zircon grains are not con-

Figure 12. Chondrite-normalized plots for zircon between 589 and 380 Ma.

nected by a fractional crystallization process (e.g., Barth and Wooden, 2010). In the U/Ce–Th graph proposed by Bacon et al. (2012) to discriminate between metamorphic and igneous zircon, zircons with ages between 589 and 510 Ma are plotted in the igneous zircon field (Fig. 13d).

From the first group of data between 589 and 510 Ma, we can extract two ages: 546 ± 5 Ma out of six analyses, and 526 ± 3 Ma from 14 analyses (Fig. 15). These magmatic ages are also recognized in other well-characterized high-P/high-T units of the allochthonous complexes (Peucat et al., 1990; Santos Zalduegui et al., 2002; Castiñeiras et al., 2010), and they are related to a magmatic arc creation around the periphery of Gondwana (Abati et al., 1999, 2007).

5.2 Evolution of metamorphism of the Sobrado migmatitic paragneiss based on zircon composition

Extracting ages from a dataset where the data are evenly distributed from 500 to 380 Ma is a challenging task. When such smear in the age sorting happens, if we can rule out analytical error, we have three possibilities (e.g., Castiñeiras et al., 2010), namely (i) the correct age is the youngest and the dispersion is related to zircon inheritance, (ii) the real age is the oldest and the spread is caused by lead loss, or (iii) the age range is recording some kind of protracted geological event. Taking into account the CL texture of the youngest spots, we can remove the first possibility as the majority of analyses were performed in zircon rims. Furthermore, maximum depositional ages obtained from similar units from the allochthonous complexes preclude their interpretation as inheritance. The second possibility is plausible, considering the complex metamorphic evolution and the high grade attained by these rocks. However, a young lead loss episode should have affected also the inherited zircon ages, and the presence of various old age peaks (e.g., ~ 2000 , 546 and 536 Ma) suggests that they did not experienced lead loss. However, we can argue that limited lead loss occurred in some grains that have similar composition

to the 589–510 Ma group ($\text{Th}/\text{U} > 0.15$) but younger ages (between 502 and 468 Ma). This group of outlier analyses (nos. 10, 11, 26 and 63) could have experienced a decoupling between their actual age and their composition (e.g., Flowers et al., 2012). Finally, we favor the last option when we take into account the strong correlation observed between age and zircon composition (Figs. 13a–c and 14).

This group of young analyses defines a trend with negative correlation from 500 to 380 Ma and Th/U values from 0.01 to 0.13. This correlation between the age and the composition of zircon suggests that the age dispersion is related to an actual geological process and is not caused by lead loss. Furthermore, even though the Th/U ratio shows a consistent evolution from 510 to 380 Ma, the rest of the proxies considered (Hf, Yb/Gd and Eu/Eu^* , Fig. 13a–c) point to a two-stage evolution, and the characteristics of the REE patterns are compatible with a metamorphic origin (Chen et al., 2009, 2010; Rubatto et al., 2009; Peters et al., 2013; Stipska et al., 2016).

This scenario is congruent with the presence of two metamorphic events in the HP-HT units: one at ~ 490 – 480 Ma and the other at ~ 390 – 380 Ma (e.g., Fernández-Suárez et al., 2002, 2007). The increase in Yb/Gd values (Fig. 13b), related to the slope of the HREE, in zircons aged from 502 to 430 Ma is congruent with a higher availability of HREE in the rock. As garnet is the most important HREE reservoir in metamorphic rocks, we argue that this behavior is the record of the progressive destabilization of garnet in a decompressive path from HP-HT conditions. The increase observed in the Eu/Eu^* ratio is consistent with a progressive destabilization of plagioclase, which is the main europium reservoir in rocks (Barth and Wooden, 2010; Castiñeiras et al., 2011).

The sharp decrease observed in the Yb/Gd ratio from 420 to 380 Ma is probably related to a new event of garnet growth (Rubatto et al., 2006; Stipska et al., 2016), i.e., the second HP-HT event. The evolution in the Eu/Eu^* ratio suggests that this event took place under granulite facies conditions, as plagioclase was present to pump out all the available europium.

5.3 Monazite and titanite geochronology: age of the youngest metamorphism in the Sobrado antiform

The youngest zircon data recorded (380 ± 4 Ma) are consistent with the monazite concordia age (382 ± 1 Ma) in the migmatitic paragneiss of the middle tectonic slice. Besides, both monazite and irregular/subround zircons share their microtextural setting along the migmatitic fabric, pointing to a coeval character with partial melting at relatively high P. Furthermore, the chemical profiles observed in the monazite suggest simultaneous crystallization of this mineral with garnet (Rubatto, 2002; Rubatto et al., 2006; Mottram et al., 2014; Holder et al., 2015). Negative Eu anomalies indicate a preferential incorporation of europium to feldspars, in particular to K-feldspar, during melt crystallization (Buick et

Table 4. REE zircon_McD_S sorted by age.

Spot	Description	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	Hf (ppm)	La (ppm)	Ce (ppm)	Pr (ppm)	Nd (ppm)	Sm (ppm)	Eu (ppm)	Gd (ppm)	Tb (ppm)	Dy (ppm)	Ho (ppm)	Er (ppm)	Tm (ppm)	Yb (ppm)	Lu (ppm)	Th/U	Yb/Gd	Eu/Eu*	Ce/Sm	Lu/Dy	U/Ce
8	c (h)	937	352	118738	0.13	29.04	3.49	9.41	45.27	22.38	337	609	1451	2381	3575	4818	5839	6870	0.38	29.63	0.18	2.66	0.47	53
36	c (h)	1837	213	191262	97.47	234.91	360.99	678.34	1304.05	710.48	980	590	691	934	1188	1866	2845	4106	0.12	0.61	0.63	0.75	0.59	13
15	r	224	30	113786	0.04	3.33	0.67	3.06	17.91	8.35	56	47	46	39	29	26	35	34	0.13	0.71	0.26	0.77	0.07	110
59	c (h)	989	54	115728	0.38	7.01	3.60	8.71	46.49	57.19	126	128	115	83	79	62	56	52	0.05	0.74	0.75	0.63	0.05	230
25	r	325	23	117864	0.04	2.64	0.48	1.38	11.35	7.99	32	36	46	60	84	155	213	309	0.07	4.06	0.42	0.96	0.67	200
76	r	223	27	121068	0.03	2.95	0.91	2.74	15.81	14.39	38	51	57	49	54	69	86	106	0.12	1.63	0.59	0.77	0.19	123
79	r	272	15	114466	0.05	0.86	0.68	1.88	7.84	6.04	40	142	277	330	292	231	177	170	0.06	2.89	0.34	0.46	0.06	514
20	r	258	17	118447	0.02	2.20	0.60	1.77	9.59	6.75	43	75	142	258	375	607	807	935	0.06	40.48	0.33	0.95	0.66	191
17	c (s)	337	12	126214	0.06	1.89	0.52	1.53	6.22	4.97	46	74	208	383	625	1263	1870	2439	0.03	29.29	0.29	1.26	1.17	291
70	r	378	7	126117	0.08	1.45	0.10	0.96	5.07	3.91	27	111	271	463	689	927	1093	1179	0.02	17.14	0.33	1.19	0.44	425
53	m	253	8	123981	0.09	1.22	0.18	0.59	4.19	3.55	35	99	235	372	541	644	652	626	0.03	13.00	0.29	1.21	0.27	338
10	c (h)	393	91	104563	0.03	57.59	0.64	2.12	9.05	6.75	66	122	283	504	813	1316	1764	2480	0.23	17.39	0.28	26.34	0.88	11
29	m	261	11	116505	0.05	3.13	0.27	0.81	3.38	3.20	32	72	179	295	488	785	1075	1488	0.04	40.00	0.31	3.84	0.83	136
71	r	301	7	123204	0.13	2.76	1.83	4.16	7.64	4.44	35	136	326	582	938	1433	1820	2276	0.02	27.14	0.27	1.50	0.70	178
26	c (s)	125	103	94660	0.13	21.86	2.38	5.86	41.08	29.66	146	227	393	625	901	1239	1553	1976	0.82	6.39	0.38	2.20	0.50	9
11	c (h)	601	358	131456	0.05	36.87	1.93	4.60	36.89	23.09	143	211	427	647	1019	1615	2373	3215	0.60	4.89	0.32	4.14	0.75	27
7	c (b)	763	40	131553	0.87	9.15	10.13	11.36	28.78	28.60	106	165	404	661	1075	1822	2658	3374	0.05	9.80	0.52	1.32	0.83	136
67	c (h)	394	4	122330	0.05	0.46	0.50	1.86	7.50	1.60	60	199	313	348	369	340	314	350	0.01	15.00	0.08	0.25	0.11	1407
75	c (o)	222	5	119417	0.26	1.11	1.01	1.77	7.09	4.44	48	157	299	366	412	413	360	423	0.02	7.65	0.24	0.65	0.14	326
47	m	173	2	120291	0.05	0.17	0.05	0.42	5.20	3.02	43	124	247	229	193	186	182	199	0.01	8.67	0.20	0.14	0.08	1619
61	c (h)	166	25	100291	0.05	12.07	0.44	1.31	10.07	7.46	46	106	241	366	534	806	1118	1398	0.15	5.52	0.35	4.97	0.58	22
63	c (h)	122	804	22524	0.74	64.11	20.58	62.36	185.81	467.14	553	861	1191	1363	1688	2126	2193	2309	6.59	1.11	1.46	1.43	0.19	3
34	o	296	229	109155	0.06	112.07	0.55	2.19	18.51	10.48	116	249	524	1007	1506	2324	2969	3943	0.77	24.81	0.23	25.07	0.75	4
74	m	48	38	92427	0.08	14.71	0.56	1.53	7.57	16.16	56	121	267	445	749	1255	1503	2114	0.78	9.09	0.79	8.05	0.79	5
12	o	74	55	84175	0.05	19.90	1.48	3.63	20.34	11.90	75	112	241	443	608	915	1286	1537	0.75	7.50	0.30	4.05	0.64	6
55	c (o)	215	71	99515	0.04	16.66	0.60	175.05	14.73	10.83	67	152	303	496	875	1215	1553	2130	0.33	12.92	0.34	4.68	0.70	21
6	c (o)	1215	931	83883	0.33	85.32	22.41	34.14	175.00	78.51	799	1127	2130	3205	4256	5980	7205	8699	0.77	12.47	0.21	2.02	0.41	23
33	o	82	69	77184	0.13	57.10	2.70	10.09	53.31	79.40	234	335	715	1081	1769	2725	3534	4634	0.84	7.16	0.71	4.44	0.65	2
13	c (o)	184	64	96602	0.01	14.68	0.51	1.20	11.08	8.88	72	122	262	467	719	1053	1360	1923	0.35	10.56	0.31	5.49	0.73	20
42	c (o)	136	114	70291	0.15	26.59	3.59	14.22	44.26	58.97	157	235	382	641	950	1547	2000	2642	0.84	6.67	0.71	2.49	0.69	8
68	c (o)	66	47	93981	0.07	23.00	0.38	2.41	8.65	11.55	39	97	172	262	478	652	842	1224	0.71	4.69	0.63	11.02	0.71	5
57	c (o)	119	117	74175	0.11	33.77	4.64	21.88	97.30	22.02	360	615	1085	1676	2350	2862	3385	3817	0.99	23.91	0.12	1.44	0.35	6
27	c (s)	61	45	90097	0.01	21.40	0.59	2.67	10.47	8.70	71	103	213	352	523	814	1056	1411	0.74	6.25	0.32	8.46	0.66	5
62	c (o)	456	176	98508	0.05	21.70	2.33	7.26	38.45	30.02	108	202	365	588	962	1421	2087	2907	0.39	4.62	0.47	2.34	0.80	34
90	m	148	95	93107	0.12	31.32	4.38	13.37	50.68	41.03	130	248	442	617	906	1360	1646	2150	0.64	6.22	0.51	2.56	0.49	8
43	c (o)	119	68	84466	0.05	11.00	0.75	3.94	22.77	27.18	77	152	326	496	773	1202	1559	2053	0.57	6.25	0.65	2.00	0.63	18
52	c (o)	113	49	110874	0.02	36.87	0.55	2.10	15.68	16.16	95	217	480	830	1400	2117	2944	4024	0.44	9.09	0.42	9.74	0.84	5
56	c (s)	37	66	90971	0.09	118.60	1.95	7.07	49.66	27.53	242	402	793	1201	1756	2275	2522	3256	1.77	13.41	0.25	9.89	0.41	1
64	c (o)	409	196	122136	0.05	45.35	0.86	3.41	20.27	1.78	101	224	480	835	1513	2275	2783	3638	0.48	30.00	0.04	9.27	0.76	15
69	c (h)	39	33	100583	0.01	19.90	0.66	1.82	12.16	14.03	57	121	226	374	623	834	1118	1553	0.84	5.25	0.53	6.78	0.69	3
14	c (h)	264	120	108355	0.01	27.08	1.31	2.47	11.35	3.91	72	116	253	449	688	1113	1404	1955	0.45	13.85	0.14	9.88	0.77	16
73	r	238	34	114369	0.09	10.28	1.86	4.97	21.62	15.81	75	189	289	447	575	810	901	1150	0.14	6.36	0.39	1.97	0.40	38
19	o	224	185	100388	0.02	38.34	1.07	3.89	27.91	9.77	136	252	569	1004	1563	2413	3019	3813	0.83	34.50	0.16	5.69	0.67	10
77	m	397	18	123301	0.38	3.07	1.47	3.00	19.12	12.43	74	158	205	203	248	331	400	423	0.05	2.48	0.33	0.66	0.21	211
78	r	157	40	85631	0.18	11.75	1.50	1.95	6.01	11.19	28	53	89	121	238	416	573	907	0.26	3.62	0.86	8.09	1.02	22
30	r (o)	270	29	111068	0.04	4.26	0.24	0.94	6.15	6.22	55	120	256	410	628	955	1137	1402	0.11	13.53	0.34	2.87	0.55	103
45	c (s)	65	29	100971	0.05	7.94	0.17	1.05	9.32	8.35	26	66	132	194	333	474	609	793	0.45	6.19	0.54	3.53	0.60	13
41	c (h)	36	16	94660	0.03	15.01	0.44	1.55	7.09	9.77	47	71	138	225	406	619	814	1061	0.45	8.64	0.53	8.76	0.77	4
9	o	53	45	82718	0.03	35.73	1.76	4.99	21.35	13.68	101	129	269	434	559	789	1106	1358	0.84	7.62	0.30	6.93	0.50	2
50	c (o)	321	114	97087	0.38	18.76	0.80	3.74	14.46	18.29	59	108	226	379	621	976	1205	1565	0.35	8.21	0.62	5.37	0.69	28
58	c (o)	463	39	113010	0.30	4.32	1.37	2.47	15.54	14.92	59	124	200	273	375	502	632	850	0.08	2.94	0.49	1.15	0.43	175
46	c (h)	275	126	105825	0.03	41.60	0.69	3.44	25.34	3.37	137	260	488	766	1288	1753	2112	2817	0.46	23.13	0.06	6.80	0.58	11
38	c (o)	48	27	84078	0.05	13.51	1.23	4.46	22.50	9.59	107	174	341	549	869	1150	1547	2033	0.56	10.87	0.20	2.49	0.60	6
31	m	41	17	108350	0.04	15.50	0.22	0.83	6.08	4.97	13	29	51	104	181	307	492	720	0.41	6.40	0.57	10.56	1.40	4
22	c (h)	128	32	95728	0.01	1.75	0.68	2.52	9.59	1.15	26	23	54	61	102	136	167	199	0.25	8.14	0.			

Figure 13. (a) Hafnium versus age, (b) Yb/Gd versus age, (c) Eu/Eu* versus age and (d) U/Ce versus Th for zircon analyses between 589 and 380 Ma.

Figure 14. Th/U ratio versus $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages for the zircon analyses from 589 to 380 Ma. Analysis 63 (510 Ma) is not represented as it has an anomalous value (6.59).

Figure 15. Weighted average obtained from magmatic ages distributed between 589 and 510 Ma.

al., 2010; Rubatto et al., 2013). These characteristics are compatible with monazite crystallization in a single pulse (MSWD < 1) in the presence of garnet, supporting its metamorphic origin. This Middle Devonian age can be interpreted to represent the minimum age of the youngest metamorphic event in the Sobrado unit, which reached high-P granulite facies (Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007; Ordóñez Casado et al., 2001). It is suggested that monazite captures the onset of the

exhumation process in the migmatitic paragneiss (Holder et al., 2015).

Titanite crystallization is syn-kinematic with the mylonitic fabric of the fine-grained amphibolites located at the base of the upper tectonic slice. The growth of titanite in amphibolitic conditions is supported by the umbrella-shaped REE patterns shown in Fig. 7b, typical of titanite coexisting with amphibole (Mulrooney and Rivers, 2005; Chambefort et al., 2013; Lesnov, 2013). A Late Devonian age (~ 365 Ma) could be related to the onset of retrograde metamorphic condi-

Figure 16. Age of the onset of the oldest HP-HT metamorphic event obtained using the TuffZirc algorithm.

tions during the development of the shear zone and suggests a prolonged exhumation process reaching amphibolite facies. The Late Devonian age lies close to the Ar–Ar exhumation ages of the uppermost units in the Órdenes Complex as recorded in the Corredoiras detachment (376 ± 2.0 Ma in hornblende; Dallmeyer et al., 1997), or in the Ponte Carreira Detachment (371 ± 4.0 Ma in muscovite; Gómez Barreiro et al. 2006).

The U–Pb zircon age for the onset of the oldest metamorphic event was estimated using the TuffZirc method, developed by Ludwig and Mundil (2002), which calculates the median by choosing the largest set of concordant analyses that are statistically coherent. The best estimate obtained for this event is $489.58 (+12.15-6.76)$ Ma, obtained by pooling together only six of 16 analyses (Fig. 16). The 510–380 Ma zircon aliquot shows a clear correlation between its cathodoluminescence texture and its geochemistry and could be also related to shielded population of “metamorphic” zircon grains within garnets (Fig. 4e). The age recorded in the migmatitic paragneiss is thought to correspond to a metamorphic event, dated in the Early Ordovician (~ 490 Ma) and is in very good agreement with upper high-P/high-T dates of equivalent units carried out during previous studies (Kuijper, 1979; Peucat et al., 1990; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2002, 2007). This age also coincides with those obtained from intermediate-P units, where large plutons were emplaced and there is a lack of later high-P/high-T metamorphism during the Devonian. The westernmost upper intermediate-P units of the Órdenes Complex underwent a granulite facies metamorphism dated between approximately 500 and 485 Ma, contemporaneous with the intrusion of massive gabbros and granodiorites related to Cambrian magmatic arc activity (Abati et al., 1999, 2003, 2007; Andonaegui et al., 2002, 2012, 2016; Castiñeiras et al., 2002, 2010). The granulite facies metamorphism is associated with heating produced by the intrusions, accompanied by a quick burial, almost coeval with igneous emplacement (Abati et al., 2003; Castiñeiras, 2005; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007).

Clearly, the metamorphic event recorded in some zircons is pre-Variscan, and it is therefore independent of the high-

P/high-T granulite facies metamorphism that occurred during the Early–Middle Devonian that has been identified in the underlying upper units, such as in Sobrado with $660-770$ °C and 13–17 kbar (Arenas and Martínez Catalán, 2002) or $750-850$ °C and 12–15 kbar (Benítez-Pérez, 2017). The pre-Variscan metamorphism was probably followed by a decompression stage, associated with partial melting (Fernández-Suárez et al., 2002). Later on, HP-HT Devonian metamorphism occurred, during which exhumation through an isothermal decompression led to partial melting in paragneiss and basic granulites (Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007). As the zircon composition and microstructural setting clearly suggest, the notable slope observed in the TuffZirc plot from 489 to 380 Ma (Fig. 16) is the result of these exhumation, burial and new exhumation processes accompanied by partial melting, in which the shielding role of garnet has been important.

6 Conclusions

This study provides new age constraints on the processes that have affected the Sobrado unit, part of the Órdenes Complex, and allows some correlation with events recognized in other parts of the allochthonous high-P/high-T complexes of NW Spain. Titanite, monazite and zircon dating together with REE analyses have been combined together in these rocks for the first time in order to carry out a geochronological investigation of the amphibolites and paragneiss.

According to the analyses, the youngest ages recorded by the metamorphic zircons are consistent with the concordia monazite age obtained from 76 analyses in the paragneiss. The microtextural setting of both metamorphic zircon and monazite along the HP-HT main foliation support that interpretation. Therefore, the Middle Devonian age (~ 380 Ma) represents the minimum age of the last Sobrado metamorphic event under high-P granulite facies conditions and represents the first stages of the Variscan orogeny in this part of Spain. Dating of metamorphic titanite in the amphibolite yields a Late Devonian age (~ 365 Ma) and is associated with very homogeneous REE patterns suggesting the prolongation of the exhumation process in the Sobrado unit, reaching amphibolite facies metamorphic conditions. In zircon, there is a strong relationship between their textures, as seen in cathodoluminescence images, REE patterns and $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages. Metamorphic zircon defines an Early Ordovician age (~ 490 Ma) although it shows a large dispersion. This date is linked to the first pre-Variscan granulite facies metamorphism seen in the Sobrado unit under intermediate-P conditions, and it is interpreted to be related to the intrusion of basic and intermediate composition rocks, and coeval with burial in a magmatic arc context. Microstructural analysis of zircon, monazite and titanite provide complementary microtextural context to understand the origin of this population

mixture. In situ dating should be conducted to confirm some textural relationships in the future.

The maximum depositional age of the Sobrado unit is suggested to be late Cambrian based on the age of the youngest inherited zircon (511 Ma). From the youngest set of inherited zircon, two ages can be obtained (546 and 526 Ma), pointing to the formation of a peri-Gondwanan magmatic arc. The protoliths of inherited zircon older than 1000 Ma from the Sobrado unit are found in other Spanish complexes and are thought to be related to sources mainly in the West African Craton.

Data availability. The data are not publicly accessible.

Author contributions. JMBP, PC, JGB and JRMC contributed equally to the fieldwork, experimental process and elaboration of the manuscript. AKC contributed to U–Pb–REE acquisition and data reduction, and RH participated in the writing of the text and the geological interpretation.

Competing interests. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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